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2015 Iran Nuclear Deal And Peace Building In The Middle East

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ABSTRACT

The paper examined the Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA), signed on 15 July 2015, to resolve the nuclear dispute involving Iran and its implications for peace and security in the Middle East. The agreement collapsed following the withdrawal of the United States in May 2018 and the re-imposition of sanctions, after which Iran scaled up nuclear activities and curtailed cooperation with the International Atomic Energy Agency. The paper was anchored on Constructivism, as advanced by Alexander Wendt, and adopted a historical research design, secondary data and qualitative content analysis. The findings showed that Western involvement shaped the early Iranian nuclear programme, that the JCPOA offered a credible framework for restraint and transparency, and that unilateral withdrawal weakened trust, multilateral diplomacy and regional stability. The paper concluded that the JCPOA remained the most viable diplomatic framework for managing the Iranian nuclear question. It recommended that the United Nations Security Council should apply global nuclear governance rules impartially, that Middle Eastern states should strengthen regional dialogue and conflict-resolution mechanisms, and that citizens and civil society should consistently pressure leaders to uphold negotiated agreements and peaceful engagement.

Keywords: JCPOA, Iran nuclear program, Middle East, peace and security, value proposition.

INTRODUCTION

The Iran nuclear program has been on the spotlight in the international community for over two decades over the contention that the program has crossed the threshold for peaceful purposes. The contention over the program was heightened from the 14th August 2002, when the National Council of Resistance of Iran, an exiled opposition group in Iran, revealed the existence of two hidden nuclear sites under construction in Iran; a uranium enrichment plant in Natanz and a heavy water facility in Arak. Also, the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) in its report of 6 June 2003, expressed concern about the possible diversion and military use of nuclear facilities, as well as the existence of many technical ambiguities (IAEA, 2003). These stunning revelations heightened the tension between Iran and US on one hand, and Iran and the international community on the other which attracted series of sanctions from UNSC, US, EU, etc. on Iran.

Surprisingly, despite the severity of the impact of the several harsh sanctions imposed on Iran by UNSC, US and the European Union (EU) and the concerted efforts by the EU through Germany, France and the United Kingdom to explore some policy options towards the peaceful resolution of the contention on the Iran nuclear program, there was no breakthrough until the resumption of diplomatic talks between US and Iran in 2013 through Presidents Barack Obama of the US and Hassan Rouhani of Iran (Reuters, 2013). This marked the beginning of the breakthrough and after several intensive negotiations between the five permanent members of the Security Council and Germany (P5+1) and Iran, the JCPOA commonly referred to as the Iran Nuclear deal was reached when all the parties agreed in Vienna on 14 July 2015 (Dahl; Pawlak, 2015). This unprecedented diplomatic ingenuity brought an end to the over thirteen years

of diplomatic impasse between Iran and the International community on one hand and Iran and the US on the other over the Iran nuclear program.

Sadly, the relief in the tensions over the Iran nuclear program following the signing of the JCPOA was short-lived when US President Donald Trump announcement on 8 May 2018, that the United States would cease to implement the JCPOA and began to impose nuclear related sanctions on Iran, primarily due to the failure of the deal to include the Iran's ballistic missile program (BBC, 2018). The sudden unilateral withdrawal of the US from the 2015 Iran nuclear deal and the re-imposition of multiple crippling economic sanctions on Iran constrained Iran to also stop to comply with the provisions of the deal, stopped cooperation with the IAEA and resumed full implementation of its nuclear program. This prevailing circumstance of the Iran nuclear program portend serious danger to peace and security in the Middle East in particular and the international community in general because the Saudi Crown Prince, Mohammed bin Salman had threatened that If Iran gets a nuclear weapon, Saudi Arabia would strive to acquire it for security reasons and for balancing power in the Middle East (Fox news, 2018).

Similarly, US President, Donald Trump had always threatened to deploy military action to restrain Iran from acquiring nuclear weapon alleging that Iran has been the leading sponsor of terrorism , and their pursuit of nuclear weapons threatens the civilized world which will not be allowed to happen (Times of Israel, 2019). Israel on its part also raised serious concern on the implications of a nuclear weapon Iran on the peace and security of the region and Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu, in his address to the 78th Session of the United Nations General Assembly said "As long as I'm Prime Minister of Israel, I will do everything in my power to prevent Iran from getting nuclear weapons (<https://haaretz.com>, 2023)".

The above unequivocal statements from Netanyahu and Donald Trump were not far fetched as they kept their words through their attacks on the Iran's nuclear and missiles infrastructure in June 2025. Iran also simultaneously carried out retaliatory strikes on Israel and US base in Qatar. These actions undoubtedly marks an escalation on the conflict over the Iran nuclear program and poses serious threat to peace and security of the Middle East.

This paper is therefore poised to review the 2015 Iran nuclear deal to meet the following objectives:

- (i) Examine the 2015 Iran nuclear deal and its value propositions to peace and security in the Middle East
- (ii) Identify the implications of the US unilateral withdrawal from the Iran nuclear deal

The value proposition of this paper stem from the fact that it provides an opportunity to leverage on the ugly impacts of the violent conflicts on the Iran nuclear program, to prevail on the key actors in these conflicts which includes Presidents, Diplomats, Opinion Leaders and the citizenry to reflect on the carnage and the dangers of perpetuating the existing scenario vis-a-vis the value propositions of a cordial relations, in a bid to explore and embrace the opportunities in Alternative Dispute Resolution mechanisms to resolve the conflict and end the lost of lives, threat to peace and security that has characterized the region. The paper further provides practical policy measures by interrogating the role of the UN in the conflict in a bid unravel the gaps in its operations that has constrained member nations to resort to self help through the acquisition of lethal weapons that threatens the peace and security of the international community.

Theoretical Framework

The paper adopted Constructivism as posited by Alexander Wendt as the theoretical framework with the central position which holds that anarchy that characterizes inter state relations is socially constructed. Constructivism as the theoretical standpoint for this study stem from a Problem Solving Approach by contending that the violent conflicts that characterize the Iran Nuclear program is socially constructed. It further holds that the contending issues were made by man and not natural forces. Hence, there are opportunities to navigate the contending issues to provide a different outcome based on the values, norms, relations, identities, etc of the purposive actors, opinion leaders and the citizenry. The study particularly took cognizance of the US - Japan relations, who were violently in opposing camps in the Second World War but have, over time, turned the situation around, to enjoy cordial relations for several decades.

Literature review

Parsi (2017) is his book " Loosing an Enemy: Obama, Iran and the Triumph of Diplomacy" examines among others, how the leaders of the P5+1 avoided the twin dangers of war and a nuclear armed Iran and

systematically documents how diplomats and negotiators made the Iran nuclear deal achievable. The book highlights the critical success factors behind the deal and the inherent learning curves that could be adopted to resolve future conflicts in the international system. More importantly, the book envisages the threats to the durability of the nuclear deal and highlights the fact that the deal will make US to lose an enemy in the Middle East or the gains in the US - Iran relations under the deal will be lost.

Huang (2016) researched on the subject titled “The Iran Nuclear Issue and Regional Security: Dilemmas, Responses and the Future”. The research examines three profound areas of the Iran nuclear program which were the history of the Iran’s nuclear program and how it escalated into a protracted and complex international conflict, how the program affected the strategic thinking and decision making on national and regional security by Iran, Israel, Saudi Arabia and US and thirdly, the uncertainties in the implementation of the hard won nuclear deal under the JCPOA, the future of the nuclear issue within a regional security framework and the role of the UN in this regard. Huang on the history of the Iran’s nuclear program and how it escalated into a protracted and complex international conflict posits that the program would likely not have become an international crisis as it has been in the past decades if not for the Islamic revolution in 1979, which fundamentally changed the political and social system in Iran and disrupted its cordial relations with the West. Huang also from the regional strategic thinking perspective asserted that the US, Israel, Saudi Arabia and its allied Arab states have diverse opinions towards the Iran nuclear program and how to mitigate it based on their peculiar situations or circumstances but often touted under the guise of regional security, peace and stability. It was therefore not out of place to see diverse opinions on the viability of the Iran nuclear deal towards the management of the conflict and building peace in the Middle East. While, on the future of the deal, Huang remarks that the Iranian nuclear talks between 2013-2015 shows that everything is possible as long as the parties concerned have strong political will and commitment to peace and development. He added that a regional security structure seems the way forward to bring about a lasting peace that the JCPOA alone cannot generate.

Farhad (2017) in his article titled “Iran’s Ballistic Missile Program: A New Case for Engaging Iran” agreed no less with Huang on the impact of Iraq – Iran war on the Iran Nuclear and Missile programs by stating “ both nuclear weapons and ballistic missiles are instruments of power that may be used as deterrent or compelling threats. They both serve to enhance the security of a state through raw power”. He further argues that in the case of Iran, the discourse of the regime’s motives has been highly politicized with rational choice theories taking a back seat. According to Farhad, consequently, two camps have emerged- the optimists and the pessimists. The former considers the Iranian regime to be a rational player driven by security concerns; the latter views it as an irrational, messianic entity seeking to maximize its power for offensive purposes.

Becks (2018) in his article titled “An International Relations Perspective on the Iran Nuclear Deal” analyzes the deeper problems of the deal from a perspective inspired by three schools of thought namely Realism, Institutionalism and Copenhagen School. In his view, from the Realists perspective, the scenario of Iran being a nuclear state is simply acceptable if not desirable in order to protect its autonomy vis-à-vis other states, each aim to acquire substantial military power which in turn provokes other states to strive to counter this power. Beck further speaking from the Institutionalism perspective posits that, rather than singling out Iran nuclear program, the preferred strategy would be to opt for a policy approach that strengthens the Non Proliferation Treaty (NPT) and envisions achieving a nuclear free Middle East. From the Copenhagen School, Beck argues that rather than blowing the Iranian nuclear program out of proportion by dealing with it as if it constituted a major security threat to global peace, the international community should de-securitize the issue by ceasing to demonize it and setting it in perspective with the Middle Eastern security complex as a whole. Beck stemming from the three schools of thought analyzed above, concluded that the Iran Nuclear Deal as couched is highly problematic since it failed to normalize relations across board, by creating a balance of power between Iran and Israel and by promoting a nuclear weapon free Middle East. This conclusion will form a critical part of this paper as there is a gap over the adequacy of the various peace initiatives such as the Paris Agreement of 2004, the P5+1 JCPOA nuclear deal, etc in capturing the security dilemma of Iran. The need to address this gap is a critical component in this paper.

The potency of the Iran Nuclear Deal in cushioning the security nightmare of the Middle East also attracted intellectual debate and though scholars have different views on the subject, there was a strong opinion that the deal was a step in the right direction despite some inadequacies. Farhad (2017) remarks on the potency of the JCPOA in view of the highly stringent IAEA verification process which makes it virtually sure that Iran would not have enough highly fissile material to produce a nuclear warhead. He was also very apprehensive on the role of the antagonists of the deal who according to him have already commenced a new round of actions against the implementation of the deal and concluded that the abrogation of the JCPOA may further destabilize the middle East. This study finds this prediction as apt because it truly captures the chaos, blood bath and seemingly endless crises that has engulfed the region in view of the multiple attacks across Middle East which includes the Israel - Hamas of Palestine war, Israel - Iran attacks and counter attacks, Israel - Houthis of Yemen strikes and counter strikes, Israel - Hezbollah of Lebanon attacks and counter attacks, the overthrow of Assad's regime in Syria and Iran's attack on the US base in Qatar in response to the US attack on Iranian nuclear facilities, etc.

History of Iran nuclear program

The nuclear program of the Islamic Republic of Iran commenced in 1957 under the Shah Mohammad Pahlavi administration with the signing of a civil nuclear cooperation agreement with the United States of America under the Atoms for Peace program through which the US provided information and equipment on nuclear technology to schools, hospitals, research institutions and the first nuclear reactors to Israel (Cohen & Burner, 2015). This was the pathway for the construction of the first nuclear research facility at Tehran which in November 1967 ran on enriched uranium (HEU) provided by the US (Iran Watch, 2025). In 1974, Shah Pahlavi proceeded to establish the Atomic Energy Agency of Iran (AEOI) to superintend over the production of substantial megawatts of electricity from the network of nuclear power plants over twenty years duration for which contracts for various aspects of the project were signed with some Western firms which includes the French based Eurodif consortium for the construction of uranium enrichment plant, Germany's Kraftwerk (Siemens) to construct pressurized water reactors at Bushehr, etc. Also, a comprehensive plans for a full domestic nuclear cycle, including uranium mining and fuel fabrication, with a new Nuclear Technology Centre established at Isfahan (Iran Watch, 2025).

However, the Iran nuclear program was aborted on the deposition of the pro Western Shah Pahlavi monarchical government in January, 1979 and the emergence of the Islamic cleric Ayatollah Ruhollah Khomeini as the new leader of Iran (Iran Watch, 2025). But, the gruesome experience of Iran in the eight years war with Iraq between 1980 - 1988, where Iraq freely deployed missile and chemical attacks on Iran led to the re-invigoration of the program about 1985 with the simultaneous construction of overt and covert projects across Iran which ultimately pitched Iran against the international community. The foregoing historical background to the Iran's nuclear program clearly indicates that the US and its Western allies such as France and Germany played critical roles in giving birth to the construction of various aspects of the program that has over time become a source of rift primarily between Iran and the US on one hand and Iran and Israel on the other.

Previous Peace initiatives on the Iran nuclear program:

The Paris Agreement of 2004 between three European Union states namely, United Kingdom, France and Germany (EU3) and the Islamic Republic of Iran was a bold step at harmonizing the rift in the US - Iran relations over the Iran nuclear program. The efforts of the EU3 states to intervene in the matter was sequel to the IAEA report in June 2003 which indicted Iran of non compliance with the Non Proliferation Treaty (NPT) and the attendant US overwhelming inclination towards taking military action and/or activate a regime change in Iran to forestall alleged Iran's surreptitious efforts towards acquiring nuclear weapon. Following the EU3 preliminary discussions with Iran in November 2004, Iran among other resolutions suspended the uranium enrichment activities and other key aspects of the program for the duration of the EU3 - Iran negotiations. The EU3 and Iran were required to build on this framework by holding further discussions towards reaching an agreement on how Iran's nuclear program will be monitored and generally build confidence for economic and security cooperation. However, the long term objective of the EU3 approach for a continuous dialogue with Iran to achieve a nuclear weapon free Iran

did not totally align with US strategic approach which relied on stringent technological restrictions on the project or direct. In this context, the insistence by the EU3 to uphold US provisions bordering on Iran's complete suspension of fuel cycle activities became a clog on the wheel of progress in advancing the EU3 negotiations with Iran.

However, the insistence to place technological restrictions outside the provisions of the NPT was counter productive because as Iran had repeatedly insisted, Article IV of the NPT supports Iran's rights "to develop, research, production, and use of nuclear energy for peaceful purposes" and until there is a verifiable violation of Article 111 of the NPT which states that these rights are conditional on the understanding that the facilities will not be used "to manufacture or otherwise acquire nuclear weapons", there was no basis to restrict the Iran nuclear program through some arbitrary regulatory frameworks as US had intended.

The letter of 8 May 2006 from the Iranian President Mahmoud Ahmadinejad to the US President George Bush (JNR) affirming Iran's readiness to engage US to resolve all issues surrounding the rift in US - Iran relations was another effort towards resolving the conflict over the Iran nuclear program. The letter from Ahmadinejad provoked intellectual debate as (Goodall; e'tal, 2008) describes it to have opened a line of moral and philosophical that appears to be aimed at cross-cultural dialogue with President Bush on vital issues. Similarly, in describing the comprehensive nature of President Ahmadinejad's letter to President Bush and the value chain it portends to the US - Iran relations, Parsi (2017) said the proposal was comprehensive as it ranges from the Palestinian-Israeli conflict, Hamas and Islamic Jihad, complete opening of the Iran nuclear program to an intrusive International Inspectors in order to alleviate any fear of Iranian weaponization, willingness to sign the additional protocols to the Non Proliferation Treaty and the readiness to open the program to US involvement but this noble gesture from Iran was blatantly rebuffed by the US.

2015 Iran nuclear deal (JCPOA)

The JCPOA reached on 14 July 2015 by the P5+1 and Iran was one of the major peace initiatives taken to resolve the rift over the Iran nuclear program. The non compliance of Iran to the terms of the Additional Protocols as proposed under the Paris Agreement of 2004 and the resolve of Iran to continue uranium enrichment and other components of the nuclear program in February 2006 (Lyons, 2015) constrained IAEA to report Iran to the UNSC which attracted the wrath of the Council to pass several resolutions and sanctions which includes 1696, 1737, 1747, 1803 and 1929 between 2006 and 2010 all aimed at compelling Iran to suspend uranium enrichment and processing until it totally complies with the IAEA Statute and the UN Charter (Kerry, 2015).

It was in the midst of this tension soaked atmosphere over the Iran nuclear program, the 44th US President, Barrack Obama on 27 September 2013 initiated a telephone conversation with the Iranian President Hassan Rouhani, the first high-level contact between US and Iranian leaders since after the 1979 Iranian revolution. The resumption of diplomatic talks between US and Iran and the several rounds of negotiations on the Iran nuclear program by the P5+1 gave birth to the Joint Plan of Action which was signed on 24 November 2013 which primarily consisted of a short-term freeze on the Iran nuclear program in exchange for a reduction on the economic sanctions on Iran (Gearan & Warrick, 2013). The negotiations on the Joint Plan of Action was ultimately extended by twenty months (November 2013 - July 2015) when all the parties agreed in Vienna on 14 July 2015 on the JCPOA (Dahl; Pawlak, 2015). The UNSC also on 20 July 2015 adopted resolution UNSCR 2231 endorsing the deal (www.reuters.com). The Iranian Parliament approved the deal on 13 October 2015, while, the US Parliament could not secure the votes to approve or disapprove from both Houses hence, the Iran nuclear agreement became effective on the expiration of the Congressional review period on 17 September 2015 (Jett, 2018). The deal resolved to constrain the Iran nuclear program by taking the following measures among others:

- Limited fuel cycle activities that could lead to the production of weapons-grade uranium or plutonium
- Restricted the number and type of centrifuges in operation, the level of uranium enrichment, and the size of Iran's enriched uranium stockpile

- Key facilities at Fodow, Natanz and Arak were repurposed for civilian uses only such as medical and industrial research
- More intrusive IAEA monitoring measures of the fuel-cycle related activities
- In exchange for Iran’s compliance to the JCPOA, it received relief from nuclear program related sanctions imposed by the UN, EU and the US

But, the antagonists of the deal also strongly advanced the following points against the deal:

- The deal ignored other Iran’s destabilizing conducts in the region such as the support for terrorist activities
- The deal failed to address the Iran’s ballistic missile program
- The deal did not sufficiently address the sunset clauses by not answering the questions around what happens after the 10-15 years validity period of the deal
- The sanctions relief simply provided Iran over US\$100 billion to advance its support for other destabilizing activities in the region

However, despite the divided opinions on the 2015 deal, this paper strongly holds that the deal was a positive development towards preventing Iran from acquiring a nuclear weapon, provided a pathway for the resolution of the rift in the US - Iran relations which was a critical step in resolving other contending issues in the region. More importantly, a negotiation of this magnitude that had defied diplomatic efforts for over a decade, built an atmosphere of bitterness and distrust among the feuding parties, should not be expected to have a zero sum outcome to either of the parties, rather, it was logical for both parties to shift grounds without losing sight of the critical success factors. The deal undoubtedly met the critical success factor for the US which was to stop Iran from acquiring a nuclear weapon that was presumed to be 2-3 months to the cross line. It is also striking to note that as at when US unilaterally withdrew from the nuclear deal, the IAEA released compliance reports between 22 February and 31 May 2019 declaring that Iran was in good standing pursuant to its IAEA agreements pertaining to verification and monitoring, heavy water processing, activities related to enrichment and fuel, centrifuge research and development, manufacturing and inventory, and transparency measures (IAEA, 2019). It is also worrisome to note that the US and the entire UNSC that has shown strong animosity towards Iran over its nuclear program turned blind eyes to Israel, another country in the Middle East, that refused to sign the Non Proliferation Treaty (NPT) and further proceeded to acquire nuclear weapons as confirmed in the table 1 below: This is a clear affirmation of application of double standards in the interpretation and application of international statutes by the relevant regulatory agencies which is dangerous for the peace and security of the international community.

Table. 4.3: Showing status of world nuclear forces 2025

Country	Deployed Strategic	Deployed non strategic	Reserve deployed non	Military stockpile	Total inventory
Russia	1,718 (c)	0(d)	2,591(c)	4,309	5,459
United States	1,670 (g)	100 (h)	1,930	3,701(i)	5,177 (j)
France	280	na	10(k)	290	290
China	24	na	576	600	600(i)
United Kingdom	120	na	105	225	225(m)
Israel	0	na	90	90	90(n)
Pakistan	0	na	170	170	170(o)
India	0	na	180	180	180(p)
North Korea	0	na	50	50	50(q)
Total	3,812	100	5,702	9,614	12,241

Source: Federation of American Scientists - fas.org

The value propositions of the 2015 Iran nuclear deal

A key outcome of the Iran nuclear deal was the provision of the platform for a positive diplomatic engagement between Iran and US as opposed to the gunboat diplomacy that was riddled with bitterness, mistrust and threats. It is striking to note that a culture of positive diplomatic engagement creates an atmosphere for mutual trust, dialogue and peaceful relations between states in the international community. A test case in this regard was the incident of 12th January 2015, when about ten US sailors, due to navigational error caused by the mechanical failure of their boat, strayed into Iranian territorial waters and were apprehended and taken hostage by the Iranian Revolutionary Guard Corp (IRGC), a military arm of the Iranian government. The US Navy on getting the report of their sailors being taken hostage by Iranian forces dispatched ships and helicopters on a military rescue mission which would have caused a serious escalation of the incident between the US and Iran. Thankfully, this incident happened at the nick of concluding the JCPOA by the P5+1 and the path to lifting some crippling sanctions on Iran, which helped Kerry and Zarif, the two foreign Ministers of US and Iran, to leverage on the prevailing warm diplomatic communication corridor to promptly resolve the conflict and secured the release of the US sailors within few hours. Hence, Kerry in expressing his gratitude over the incident affirmed the beauty of diplomacy over rift thus:

I want to express my gratitude to Iranian authorities for their cooperation in swiftly resolving this matter. That this issue was resolved peacefully and efficiently, is a testament to the critical role diplomacy plays in keeping our country safe, secure, and strong (<https://2009-2017.state.gov/secretary-/remarks/2016/01/251139.htm>).

Also, the 2015 Iran nuclear deal had the potentials of boosting US - Iran relations over the overlapping goals of defeating ISIS terrorist activities in Iraq and Syria by making the fight a security policy priority and committing huge financial and material resources into it. For instance, although the decision and the modalities towards defeating ISIS in Iraq and Syria by the US and Iran were taken independent of each other but they had a common goal which was to defeat ISIS activities in the region particularly in Iraq. The role played by Iran in the fight against ISIS in Iraq helped to stabilize the US instituted post Saddam Hussein's government in Iraq and the Iraqi President Fuad Masum, acknowledged it and praised Iran as the first country to provide weapons to Iraq to fight the ISIS Takfiri terrorists (Al-Alam, 2014). Hence, the sustenance of the Iran nuclear deal would have strengthened the collaboration between US, Iran and other regional neighbors towards building a common front in confronting the menace of terrorist activities in the region.

The Iran nuclear program was a critical factor that has strained Iran - US relations which has in turn served as a life wire for the multiple conflicts that bedeviled the Middle East as both countries were either directly or indirectly involved in most of the conflicts in the region through the provision of tacit military, technical, logistics or financial support to the opposing sides of most of the conflicts. Hence, a cordial US - Iran relations through the Iran nuclear deal would have automatically reduced the tension and acrimony that characterizes the region as applicable under Iran's Pahlavi administration which enjoyed the support of US and cordial relations with Israel and most other states in the Middle East. Also, a cordial US - Iran relations would have drastically cut the source of military support and other forms of financial and tactical support most of these militant groups receive from Iran as part of Iran's forward looking strategy to engage and exhaust the military strength of its enemies such as US and Israel outside the Iranian soil.

On the economic front, according to a 2014 study of the National American Council, the US sanctions on Iran cost the US over \$175 billion in lost trade and 279,000 lost job opportunities (Tehran Times, 2014). It was widely argued that if Iran and the US were to achieve a diplomatic breakthrough, it would not only sharply reduce the tension in the region, but would further push Iran to the status of an emerging market on its own right (Business Monitor International, 2014). It is therefore evident that a cordial US - Iran relations will end the regime of US multiple primary and secondary crippling economic sanctions on Iran which will open the economy to fully participate in the global economic market and optimize its enormous potentials in the oil, gas and other minerals to boost its economy as applicable between 1980 - 1999 when Iran had the highest nominal GDP in the Middle East (see table 2 below).

A boost in the Iranian economy under a cordial US - Iran relations would also provide economic opportunities to other states in the Middle East, US and the international community. For instance the entry of Iranian oil and gas to the global market would help to boost supply and stabilize the price of oil and gas. According to OPEC's Monthly Oil Report for June 2025, Iran's daily production capacity was 2.5 million barrels per day against the production quota of 3.84 million barrels per day by OPEC with over 100 million barrels of unsold floating oil which was the highest in the industry due to the economic sanctions on Iran. A cordial US - Iran relations will not only end this ugly trend but would automatically provide the market for full utilization of Iran's oil and further improve its production capacity to optimize the OPEC quota to stabilize the global oil market. The point being made here is that in place of the endless violent conflicts and the attendant deaths and devastation that characterize the rift in the US - Iran relations over the Iran nuclear program, on the contrary, a cordial US - Iran relations has the potentials for peace, stability and enormous economic gains to the Middle East in particular and the international community in general.

Implications of the US unilateral withdrawal from the Iran nuclear deal

The US unilateral withdrawal from the deal has created a vacuum for Iran to pursue its nuclear weapon ambition without the necessary checks and balances provided by the 2015 nuclear deal. Iran's cessation of all forms of cooperation with the IAEA, the removal of the monitoring equipment installed by the agency under the provisions of the deal and the return to full enrichment of uranium clearly leads Iran to the path of acquisition of nuclear weapons which is dangerous for the peace and security of the region in particular and the international community in general. It has also heightened the tension between Iran and Israel, on one hand and Iran and the US on the other as exemplified in the multiple violent conflicts that has erupted in the region between 2020 -2025 which includes the US assassination of the Iranian Revolutionary Guard Commander, General Soleimani in 2020, the Hamas - Israeli Gaza war since October 2023, Israel - Hezbollah attacks, Israel - Houthis of Yemen attacks, Israel - Iran attacks in June 2025, the US - Iran attacks in June 2025, etc. These violent conflicts have suddenly returned the Middle East to a theatre of wars.

The crippling economic sanctions imposed by US on Iran has devastating effects not only on Iran but also the economic viability of the Middle East. Going by table 2 below, between 1980 - 1989, Iran was the biggest economy in the Middle East with a nominal Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of over USD244B annually which was over 100% higher than the GDP of the second and third highest states in the region which were Saudi Arabia and Turkey respectively. But, with the rift over the Iran nuclear program and the multiple economic sanctions on Iran by the US, Iran's GDP as provided on table 3 slide to the third position between 2010-2019 with a GDP of about USD483B and also about half of the USD758B GDP of Turkey, the topmost state in the region. The economic sanctions on Iran has deprived the region from the economic boost and development the region would have attracted under a complementary and healthy economic competition. Hence, unlike the 2015 Iran nuclear deal which paved the way for social stability, peace, security and enormous economic gains in the Middle East, the US unilateral withdrawal from the deal is characterized with the endless violent conflicts and the attendant deaths, devastation, poverty and insecurity in the region.

Table 2: The GDP of the top 7 countries in the Middle East from 1980 - 1989

Name of Country	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	Average
Iran	116.9	123.9	153.5	191.5	197.4	220.3	254.9	338.1	380.7	463.1	244.0
Saudi Arabia	164.5	184.3	153.2	129.2	119.6	103.9	86.9	85.6	88.1	95.2	121.1
Turkey	96.6	97.9	88.9	84.9	82.7	92.9	102.4	118.9	125.1	147.8	103.8
Egypt	23.5	25.8	30.2	37.3	41.9	48.8	54.1	77.4	92.5	115.4	54.7
UAE	41.7	46.5	43.2	39.6	39.2	38.5	30.5	33.5	34.1	39.3	38.6
Israel	25.0	26.5	28.4	31.7	30.0	27.9	34.4	41.0	50.8	51.7	34.8
Kuwait	0	25.2	21.6	20.9	21.7	21.4	17.9	22.4	20.7	24.3	19.6

Source: Data obtained from World economic outlook database October 2025 www.imf.org

Table 3: The GDP of the top 7 countries in the Middle East from 2010 - 2019

Name of Country	21010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	Average
Turkey	783.0	843.3	882.4	962.5	943.3	868.2	870.3	863.9	807.3	775.2	859.9
Saudi Arabia	528.2	680.6	751.9	769.8	787.2	693.4	689.3	741.3	886.6	888.9	741.7
Iran	598.6	722.1	487.1	494.6	532.1	471.4	477.6	507.8	343.7	252.2	488.7
UAE	307.7	368.9	392.8	409.6	424.9	382.0	381.7	403.4	440.6	433.9	394.6
Israel	239.4	267.7	263.2	298.0	314.4	302.8	321.1	357.4	375.5	399.2	313.6
Egypt	230.0	247.7	294.5	303.2	321.6	350.0	351.4	246.8	263.2	317.9	292.7
Iraq	138.5	185.8	218.0	234.6	234.7	177.6	168.4	190.0	230.2	236.7	201.5

Source: Data obtained from World economic outlook database October 2025 www.imf.org

CONCLUSIONS

The study revealed that the Iran nuclear program, at inception, was midwived by the US and its western allies such as France, Germany, Israel, etc that handled various Engineering, Procurement and Construction (EPC) aspects of the program under the Western aligned monarchical leader, Shah Pahlavi of Iran. Hence, the program became a sour grape to US and its Western allies because of the Iranian revolution of 1979 which heralded an anti western Islamic government in Iran under the leadership of Ayatollah Khomeini. The paper also finds the role of the United Nations on the Iran nuclear program highly worrisome in the sense that while the agency hurriedly aligned with the US persuasion to impose economic sanctions on Iran to ensure compliance to the non proliferation treaty, it turned blind eyes to Israel, a contending state in the power equation in the Middle East that did not only refuse to sign the non proliferation treaty but also proceeded to acquire nuclear weapons without any hindrance. This act clearly depict the application of double standards in the handling global security issues which is dangerous.

Also, in all the major peace initiatives such as the 2004 EU3 Agreement and the 2015 Iran Nuclear Deal, it was the US that ultimately frustrated the optimization of the opportunities by either making untenable demands such as the insistence on zero enrichment of uranium or walking out from duly signed peace deal even when the terms of the deal were religiously adhered to by Iran. The value proposition of the 2015 Iran nuclear deal in building peace in the Middle East, was evident on the prompt resolution of the conflict between US and Iran over the twelve US sailors that strayed into the Iranian waters at the nick of concluding the JCPOA in 2015, the successes achieved in the common vision by US and Iran over the fight towards curtailing the menace of ISIS in Iraq and Syria as sufficient assurance for remarkable improvements in the peace and stability of the Middle East and the opportunities in the robust economy of

Iran between 1980 - 1999 and the potential knock on effect on the economies of the rest of the states in the region as sufficient pathway to building peace and security in the Middle East.

The implications of the continuous rift in the US - Iran relations towards building peace in the Middle East aptly includes the perpetuation of the vicious cycle of conflicts, wars, deaths, destruction, poverty, underdevelopment and instability in the region. This gloomy picture was borne from the dogged nature of the opposing factions and their allies in the region, the lethal arms and ammunition in the possession of these opposing camps, the technological breakthrough that has characterized the twenty first century and the unmitigated efforts of man towards the acquisition of weapons of mass destruction to have an edge over their opponents poses serious danger to the peace and security of the Middle East.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The paper recommends as follows:

- (i) The UNSC should be fair to all states in the international community in the enforcement of its statutes and allied regulatory frameworks such as the Non Proliferation Treaty. A situation where it allows Israel, a contending power in the Middle East, to possess nuclear weapon capability without any hindrance but turn round to brutally confront Iran, which is another contending power in the same geographical region over its quest to possess the same nuclear weapon capability is a clear application of double standards which is counter productive and have the tendency of overheating the international polity.
- (ii) The states in the Middle East should reflect on the impact of the violent conflicts and wars to the region which ranges from the loss of millions of lives, destruction of property worth trillions of dollars, refugee crises, hunger, malnutrition, poverty, underdevelopment and the threat to peace and security and explore the need for alternative conflict resolution mechanisms to settle their differences to save the region from further devastation.
- (iii) There is the urgency for the citizens in the international community to hold their respective leaderships accountable for decisions that flagrantly defy natural justice, peace and stability to avoid violent conflicts and wars which are not the viable path to peace and security. Hence, the need to prevail on leadership to always embrace dialogue, respect and abide by duly signed peace treaties and agreements to forestall the relapse to avoidable violent conflicts and wars as exemplified in the US abrupt withdrawal from the Iran nuclear deal.

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